

Muon-Neutrino Inclusive Cross-Sections Across CH, Fe, Pb, C and H₂O at MINERvA

Akeem L Hart (On behalf of the MINERvA collaboration)
Supervisor: Dr Abbey Waldron

1. MINERvA

- MINERvA is a high-statistics neutrino experiment at Fermilab designed to explore how different nuclei affect neutrino interactions.
- It's on-axis in the NuMI neutrino beam and is constructed with several target materials (CH, Fe, Pb, C, He, Water), allowing for direct comparisons in the same well-studied beam. [1]
- MINERvA utilised the MINOS near detector for muon tagging.

2. Analysis Overview

- Inclusive cross-section measurements for **muon neutrino** interactions across **CH, Fe, Pb, C and Water**
- Analysis uses NuMI medium energy (ME) run (Peak $E_\nu \approx 6$ GeV) 10.6×10^{20} POT \rightarrow High statistics in an interesting region.
- Reconstruction utilises a new Domain Adversarial Neural Network (DANN) approach.
- Will be MINERvA's first water results for medium energy inclusive ν_μ , which could be particularly useful to water-based programs.

Deliverables:

- 1D Cross Sections:
 - Muon Energy
 - Recoil energy
 - Bjorken X
 - Muon longitudinal momentum
 - Muon transverse momentum
- 2D Cross Sections:
 - Muon longitudinal momentum vs muon transverse momentum.

3. Water Target Treatment

- Water results are of particular interest to water-based experiments and associated modelling.
- MINERvA's water target differs from the other targets in this analysis and consequently requires modified treatment.
- We employ a subtractive approach to separate the actual water from everything else.

4. Event Selection

Target Definition:

We include the neighbouring scintillator planes in target definition to capture mis-reconstructed events. [2]

5. Status and next steps

- Machinery to extract cross sections, perform sideband tuning and background subtractions has been implemented.

Immediate Next Steps:

- Wrap up investigations of ML Reconstruction uncertainty - especially in the water target region
- Fake data studies
- Model comparisons

[1] Aliaga, L et al. (MINERvA Collaboration), Design, calibration, and performance of the MINERvA detector, Nucl. Instrum. Methods Phys. Res., Sect. A 743, 130 (2014).
[2] Klustová, A. Measurement of Nuclear Dependence in Inclusive Antineutrino Scattering. Ph.D Thesis. Imperial College London. (2024)